

Profitability Analysis of Select Steel Companies in India (With special reference to companies listed in BSE)

OPEN ACCESS

Volume : 7

Special Issue : 1

Month : February

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2320-4168

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Chellasamy, P &
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“Profitability Analysis
of Select Steel
Companies in India.”
*Shanlax International
Journal of Commerce*,
vol. 7, no. S1, 2019,
pp. 1–12.

DOI:

[https://doi.org/10.5281/
zenodo.2552187](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2552187)

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Abstract

Indian steel industry plays a significant role in the country's economic growth. India is the fifth largest steel producer at the global front and struggling to become the second largest producer in the years to come. An exhaustive research has been done on Indian steel industry. It classifies the finished steel product market into two categories - Alloy and Non-alloy and covers information on industry-wise steel demand, overall steel consumption, production, and trading market. Besides, it provides industry forecast for different market segments. A projected research work said that Indian crude steel production would grow at a CAGR of around 10% during 2010-2013. Moreover, with the government proactive incentive plans to boost economic growth by injecting funds in various industries, such as construction, infrastructure, automobile, and power will drive the steel industry in future.

Keywords: BSE, Profitability, Unit root test, Co integration test.

Introduction

India's economic growth is contingent upon the growth of the Indian Steel Industry. Consumption of steel is taken to be an indicator of economic development. Indian Steel Industry is one of the pillars of Industrial Revolution occupies a key position in modern Industrial society and has come to symbolize the prowess of Industrial nations. The Indian Steels cape is changing rapidly. The Steel Industry has emerged in a big way to India's evolving stature as an economic power.

While steel continues to have a stronghold of traditional sectors such as construction, housing and ground transportation, special steels are increasingly used in engineering industries such as power generation, petrochemicals and fertilizers. India occupies a central position on the global steel map, with the establishment of new state-of-the art of steel industries, acquisition of global scale capacities by players continuous modernizations and up-gradation of older plants, improving energy efficiency and backward integration into global raw material sources.

The performance of a company in the above areas would be naturally reflected in the financial statement of the respective Industries. Financial statements are the summary of various financial activities which provide information in convenient form. By analyzing these financial statements and evaluating the relationship between the various components, a company's profitability position and performance could be easily interpreted.

Review of Literature

Amir Hossein Jamali and Asghar a Sadi (2012) in their research entitled "management efficiency and profitability in Indian automobile industry", examined the relationship between the management efficiency and the firms profitability for a sample of 13 auto manufacturing companies listed on the Bombay stock exchange, located in pune for the period of five years from 2006-2010. The analysis is carried out using Minitab 14 and conducting Pearson coefficient correlation test on variables of the including gross profit ratio and assets turnover ratio. The authors concluded that the central conclusion of the study is profitability and management efficiency are highly correlated to each other. The recommendations for improving the management efficiency and profitability in this industry are suggested.

Kavitha and Palanivelu (2014) in their study explained that iron and steel industry is important for the economic development of a country in terms of foreign ex-change, employment generation, infrastructure development and technology. This study confines itself to the issues relating to the financial performance of the iron and steel industries with regard to its growth, profitability and liquidity and the impact on various factors such as capital, liquidity position of iron and steel industry for the period of ten years from 2002 – 2003 to 2011 – 2012.

Mohan Kumar M.S Vasu V and T. Aswatha Narayana (2016) This paper is focused on examining liquidity and profitability position of SAIL using the ratios like CR, QR, ROTA, ROCE, RONW, GPR, NPR, OPR and EPS. The financial health of the company is examined using Altman's Z score model. Liquidity is playing major role to meet the short term obligations on time for the business. Regular Payment of interest and principal amount of long term debts shows the creditworthiness of the company. Steel industry required large amount of investment, to getting this requirement creditworthiness and profitability of the company playing a crucial role in the process of decision making of the shareholders. To maintaining the proper liquidity will minimize the risk of insolvency and it give a direction to maximize profitability through maintaining creditworthiness in the market. The liquidity, profitability and financial health are the key indicators of the company to predict the future. The study reveals there is a positive correlation between liquidity and profitability ratios except ROTA and the calculated Z score values indicates company is in healthy zone.

Statement of the Problem

Indian steel industry requires large capital investment which a developing country Steel is a critical industry in worldwide, and steel products are a heavily traded commodity. In recent years, market changes, shifts in import and export levels, and weakness in the global demand for steel have negatively impacted steel industries across the India. Along with shifting trade patterns, world benchmark steel prices have been trending downward since early 2011, and the financial outlook for many steel companies has declined. The 2008-2009 global financial crises were particularly difficult for steel industries, and this period will feature prominently in the following discussion of global steel indicators. 2015 was also a period of decline for the steel industry, as weak global demand caused declines in other indicators. Based on the above research has framed following research question,

- What is the Profitability position of the steel companies in India?

Research Objectives

- To analyze the profitability of select steel companies in India.
- To offer suggestions for the future development of the company.

Hypothesis

H0 1: There is no Panel Unit root for the times series variables.

H0 2: There is no Panel Co integration relationship between the Profitability ratios.

Methodology

Sources of data

The data used for the study are Secondary in nature. A purposive sample of fifteen companies quoted at Bombay stock exchange has been taken based on the market capitalization. The required data were collected from the corporate database (Prowess) of the Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy (CMIE) and other relevant data are collected from moneycontrol.com, journals, magazines, reports and websites.

Period of the Study

The study covers a period of 10 years from 2006 – 2007 to 2015 – 2016.

Sampling Design

The sample company are selected on the basis of top 15 companies in purposive sampling based on the market capital have selected.

The following companies have been selected for the study;

1. Tata Steel Limited	9. Usha Martin Limited
2. JSW Steel Limited	10. Welspun Corporation Limited
3. Steel Authority of India Ltd	11. Mukand Steel Limited
4. Star Ferro Alloys Limited	12. APL Apollo Limited
5. VISA Steel	13. Jindal Steel Limited
6. Bhushan Steel	14. Ashirwad Steels Industries Ltd
7. Jindal Saw Steel Limited	15. Bajaj Steel Industries Limited
8. Ferro Alloys Corporation Ltd	

Frame Work of Analysis

For the purpose of this analysis various accounting and statistical techniques have been used. To analyse the profitability of the study, it makes use of various ratios extensively. The statistical techniques used are arithmetic mean, standard deviation, Co-efficient of variation, Compound annual growth rate Panel unit root tests and Co integration Test is used to measure the relationship of each ratio among different categories of steel industry.

Limitations of the Study

The following are the limitations of the study.

- The present study is based on ratio analysis which has its own limitations.
- The study is based on the secondary data as such its findings depend entirely on the accuracy of such data.

Gross Profit Ratio

Table 1 Summaries Statistics of Gross Profit Ratio of the select Steel Companies in India during the period from 2006-2007 to 2015-2016

(In Percentage)

Year	Tata Steel	JSW Steel	Sail	Star Ferro	VISA Steel	Bhushan	Jindal Saw	Ferro Alloys	Usha Martin	Welspun steel	Mukand	APL Apollo	Jindal Steel	Ashirwad Steel	Bajaj Steel
2006-2007	24.95	20.63	18.94	24.49	18.01	18.26	14.54	23.47	36.85	24.83	18.01	25.51	16.18	19.19	15.48
2007-2008	25.11	25.37	22.74	26.75	14.11	25.56	18.84	23.81	24.04	21.50	14.13	24.97	16.07	16.76	15.52
2008-2009	20.66	29.74	17.34	21.88	15.01	30.55	20.38	19.19	32.18	18.70	11.97	24.29	13.42	18.61	18.05
2009-2010	18.63	33.74	16.42	17.38	14.77	27.36	21.27	16.76	30.13	15.49	11.19	23.53	15.35	22.50	17.50
2010-2011	17.42	32.87	16.96	16.37	14.88	21.26	16.18	15.43	30.73	15.28	10.51	19.05	12.98	21.56	19.05
2011-2012	18.49	29.26	18.41	15.48	15.52	21.70	18.08	18.61	37.64	18.80	10.42	18.76	15.29	18.54	20.53
2012-2013	21.89	30.76	21.53	14.23	16.52	25.69	22.94	15.71	37.50	16.64	12.53	20.44	18.67	19.23	18.08
2013-2014	16.71	28.06	10.99	18.31	13.63	27.92	22.50	15.71	37.03	19.54	17.06	19.33	18.88	21.28	17.68
2014-2015	24.98	34.43	20.89	22.38	22.14	28.78	20.23	21.83	32.51	18.53	14.43	24.29	18.35	18.34	16.09
2015-2016	27.31	25.66	13.32	17.99	19.28	27.07	18.21	18.54	23.23	14.64	16.38	22.46	16.27	19.28	18.69
Mean	22.61	29.05	17.75	19.53	16.39	25.42	19.32	18.91	32.18	18.40	13.66	22.26	16.15	19.53	17.97
SD	3.41	4.29	3.63	4.13	2.68	3.84	2.68	3.18	5.34	3.13	2.78	2.63	2.04	1.74	1.52
CV	16.55	14.78	20.46	21.14	16.34	15.12	13.88	16.80	16.58	16.99	20.32	11.81	12.65	8.90	8.47
CAGR	0.04	0.02	-0.03	-0.03	0.01	0.03	0.02	-0.02	-0.05	-0.01	-0.01	-0.01	0.00	0.00	0.02

Source: Compiled and calculated from the data published in CMIE and moneycontrol.com

Table 1 reveals the gross profit ratio of select steel companies in India from 2006-2007 to 2015-2016. The average gross profit ratio of steel companies shows a fluctuating trend during the study period. The Usha Martin Limited has the highest average of 32.18 percent, followed by the JSW Steel Industries which has the average of 29.05 percent. The Mukand steels ltd has lowest average of 13.66 percent. Its decrease the gross profit ratio by low cost of the goods it sells or by using higher quality, and thus more expensive, materials to make the goods. Lower prices attract new customers.

Usha martin ltd has the highest standard deviation of 5.34 percent, followed by the JSW Steel Industries which has the standard deviation of 4.29 percent. The Ashirwad Steels Limited has the lowest standard deviation of 1.74 percent and it is found stable in gross profit ratio.

Welspun Steel Limited has the highest co-efficient of variation of 16.99 percent, followed by Ferro Alloys steel ltd of 16.80 percent. Bajaj steel ltd has the lowest co-efficient of variation of 8.47 percent.

Tata steel has the highest Compound annual growth rate of 0.04 percent, followed by Bhushan steel ltd at 0.03 percent. Usha martin ltd has the lowest Compound annual growth rate of -0.05 per cent during the study period.

Operating Profit Ratio

Table 2 Summaries Statistics of Operating Profit Ratio of the select Steel Companies in India during the period from 2006-2007 to 2015-2016

(In Percentage)

Year	Tata Steel	JSW Steel	Sail	Star Ferro	VISA Steel	Bhushan	Jindal Saw	Ferro Alloys	Usha Martin	Welspun steel	Mukand	APL Apollo	Jindal Steel	Ashirwad Steel	Bajaj Steel
2006-2007	10.65	11.87	5.06	3.5	3.69	6.47	8.12	9.73	12.35	9.03	5.13	6.08	7.36	6.19	6.38
2007-2008	12.5	15.44	4.79	6.27	2.75	0.5	4.1	9.33	10.46	6.35	6.96	5.45	7.71	4.86	8.53
2008-2009	11.05	17.82	1.15	5.31	3.42	6.12	6.23	5.33	9.73	4.25	4.14	5.18	6.21	5.99	6.49
2009-2010	7.09	22.27	1.37	3.21	2.24	3.59	6.28	3.73	5.68	2.56	4.42	3.18	3.62	6.22	7.56
2010-2011	7.51	21.4	2.46	1.94	3.29	2.36	3.65	4.23	6.68	3.64	4.62	2.46	4.62	8.46	5.94
2011-2012	8.59	19.4	4.67	2.03	7.38	4.23	7.35	7.26	15.17	7.25	3.58	4.16	5.59	5.99	4.58
2012-2013	11.56	20.08	6.66	2.07	7.77	4.28	7.59	4.35	19.23	5.54	2.15	4.15	9.51	7.85	6.05
2013-2014	7.83	17.52	5.36	6.65	6.35	5.36	14.67	4.86	18.22	8.36	10.71	4.28	5.24	6.59	5.49
2014-2015	14.61	24.25	9.39	9.95	11.25	4.18	13.93	8.64	14.07	8.19	4.95	6.77	7.31	5.26	6.41
2015-2016	18.42	15.94	8.25	6.37	5.65	5.89	11.83	7.45	13.07	5.98	3.07	6.39	6.81	3.82	5.67
Mean	10.98	18.60	4.57	4.73	5.78	4.30	7.68	6.49	12.39	6.12	5.65	4.81	6.40	6.12	6.31
SD	3.56	3.65	2.93	2.63	3.39	1.84	4.49	2.26	4.47	2.15	3.24	1.41	1.71	1.35	1.10
CV	32.42	19.65	64.02	55.63	58.68	42.76	58.50	34.83	36.06	35.23	57.37	29.25	26.29	22.62	17.37
CAGR	0.06	0.03	0.05	0.06	0.04	-0.01	0.04	-0.03	0.01	-0.04	-0.04	0.00	-0.01	-0.05	-0.01

Source: Compiled and calculated from the data published in CMIE and moneycontrol.com.

It is observed from table 2 that the operating profit ratio of selected steel companies in India from 2006-2007 to 2015-2016. The average operating profit ratio of steel companies shows a fluctuating trend during the study period. The JSW Steel has the highest average of 18.60 percent, followed by the Usha Martin Limited which has the average of 12.39 percent. The SAIL has the lowest Average of 4.57 percent.

The Jindal Saw has the highest standard deviation of operating profit ratio of 4.49percent, followed by the Usha Martin Limited which has the standard deviation of 4.47percent. The Bajaj steel ltd has the lowest standard deviation of 1.10 percent.

Steel authority of India Limited has the highest co-efficient of variation of 64.02percent, followed by VISA Steel Limited of 58.68 percent. Bajaj Steel Limited has the lowest co-efficient of variation of 17.37 percent and it is found that there is consistency in operating profit ratio.

Tata Steel Limited and Star Ferro Limited has highest Compound annual growth rate of 0.06 percent, followed by SAIL of 0.05 percent. Ashirwad steel ltd has negative Compound annual growth rate of -0.05 per cent during the study period.

Net Profit Ratio

Table 3 Summaries Statistics of Net Profit Ratio of the select Steel Companies in India during the period from 2006-2007 to 2015-2016

(In Percentage)

Year	Tata Steel	JSW Steel	Sail	Star Ferro	VISA Steel	Bhushan	Jindal Saw	Ferro Alloys	Usha Martin	Welspun steel	Mukand	APL Apollo	Jindal Steel	Ashirwad Steel	Bajaj Steel
2006-2007	11.33	4.06	2.94	3.29	1.54	5.34	6.59	1.49	-09.74	1.59	0.63	1.94	-5.74	1.19	0.62
2007-2008	15.62	3.39	2.82	-1.19	1.78	6.86	8.34	3.01	0.91	-0.88	-0.91	1.68	-7.34	-3.38	0.98
2008-2009	16.78	3.84	3.22	-2.68	2.54	7.54	9.45	4.61	-0.88	1.05	0.88	2.98	-9.84	-4.93	-0.89
2009-2010	17.34	4.22	5.86	4.98	2.95	8.79	10.89	5.79	0.93	-0.92	-1.83	3.49	-10.36	-5.48	0.49
2010-2011	18.78	4.92	6.93	-6.59	3.88	9.88	11.06	7.57	1.15	0.83	-2.8	4.3	14.62	-6.96	-0.22
2011-2012	19.73	5.07	7.94	7.34	-8.7	10.29	4.31	-0.69	0.23	1.12	-3.6	2.65	15.82	-576	2.28
2012-2013	13.25	5.07	4.46	-8.61	-7.65	8.45	3.44	4.82	0.78	0.8	-1.85	2.15	10.64	1.53	-1.49
2013-2014	15.37	2.94	5.6	7.45	-4.36	0.64	2.61	4.81	-7.8	-3.36	-3.46	1.27	8.88	-2.46	3.01
2014-2015	15.41	4.7	4.57	4.5	-6.18	-11.77	3.97	3.16	-11.73	-0.31	0.55	1.55	-2.32	-2.51	0.6
2015-2016	12.82	5.53	3.71	5.26	2.36	4.05	4.25	2.13	-11.89	2.46	0.49	1.6	-8.11	0.91	0.92
Mean	15.94	4.20	4.71	0.04	-8.39	2.20	6.49	3.78	-3.29	-0.47	-1.42	2.36	0.63	-6.15	0.63
SD	2.25	1.05	1.89	7.73	12.83	11.32	3.21	2.30	5.13	1.52	1.55	0.98	10.62	18.27	1.34
CV	14.08	24.99	40.09	14.71	-52.84	15.33	49.50	61.02	-55.83	-22.58	-18.78	41.44	16.57	-31.38	-22.57
CAGR	0.01	0.03	0.02	0.05	-0.04	-0.03	-0.04	0.04	0.02	0.04	-0.02	-0.02	0.04	-0.03	0.04

Source: Compiled and calculated from the data published in CMIE and moneycontrol.com

The table 3 reveal that the Net Profit Ratio of selected Steel Companies in India from 2006-2007 to 2015-2016. The average of Net Profit ratio of steel companies shows a fluctuating trend during the study period. Tata Steel Limited has the highest average of 15.94 percent. The Ashirwad steel ltd has negative average of -6.15 percent.

The Ashirwad Steel Limited has the highest standard deviation of 18.27 percent, followed by the Bhushan Steel Limited which has the standard deviation of 11.32 percent. The JSW Steel Limited has lowest standard deviation of 1.05 percent.

Ferro alloys Limited has the highest co-efficient of variation of 61.02 percent, followed by Jindal Saw Steel Limited of 49.50 percent. Usha martin steel has the negative co-efficient of variation of -55.83 percent.

Star Ferro Limited has the highest Compound Annual Growth Rate of 0.05 percent, followed by the Welspun Steel Limited and Bajaj Steel Limited which has the Compound Annual Growth Rate of 0.04 percent. The VISA steel ltd and Jindal Saw steel ltd has the negative Compound Annual Growth Rate of -0.04 per cent during the study period.

Return on Investment

Table 4 Summaries Statistics of Return on Investment Ratio of the select Steel Companies in India during the period from 2006-2007 to 2015-2016

(In Percentage)

Year	Tata Steel	JSW Steel	Sail	Star Ferro	VISA Steel	Bhushan	Jindal Saw	Ferro Alloys	Usha Martin	Welspun steel	Mukand	APL Apollo	Jindal Steel	Ashirwad Steel	Bajaj Steel
2006-2007	12.08	10.95	14.94	17.82	13.19	10.47	11.72	5.74	15.42	13.19	10.04	19.1	17.12	12.06	11.05
2007-2008	31.29	25.18	17.77	22.15	-18.61	0.82	-3.01	6.29	10.21	16.74	12.46	20.96	15.61	13.34	11.2
2008-2009	13.12	30.53	9.82	7.36	1.57	10.54	7.43	5.18	19.61	4.05	12.39	17.58	6.47	8.42	7.65
2009-2010	12.06	40.33	-6.24	3.96	7.65	6.86	4.46	5.42	11.08	5.43	12.46	9.48	-14.88	10.6	11.85
2010-2011	12.92	24.57	1.14	13.25	11.2	6.53	-2.77	5.2	13.63	9.84	15.54	7.78	0.92	8.11	6.86
2011-2012	13.84	24.21	10.88	13.93	39.57	9.16	32.85	19.21	41.56	17.52	7.92	12.34	14.17	12.99	10.54
2012-2013	18.08	25.71	30.41	19.65	30.24	11.2	41.83	5.24	39.45	13.02	4.37	15.96	28.95	7.56	15.1
2013-2014	18.42	15.1	-9.97	51.9	21.33	12.66	28.39	5.24	28.25	18.76	5.06	14.17	15.85	9.61	17.77
2014-2015	24.49	31.69	28.33	51.22	35.39	11.85	32.11	28.55	10.34	20.98	5.37	35.04	26.43	7.43	21.15
2015-2016	20.06	23.06	12.59	23.96	26.73	12.57	24.26	10.34	9.64	15.65	9.05	21.05	21.35	9.63	15.86
Mean	16.69	25.13	10.97	22.52	17.15	7.77	15.38	9.64	19.92	13.52	7.66	17.35	11.90	9.98	12.90
SD	6.61	8.24	13.24	16.51	17.80	7.90	18.61	7.97	12.24	5.61	6.98	7.70	13.14	2.20	4.50
CV	39.63	32.78	120.68	73.32	83.79	101.67	26.98	82.71	61.46	41.49	91.15	44.38	23.41	22.07	34.89
CAGR	0.05	0.08	-0.02	0.03	0.07	0.02	0.08	0.06	-0.05	0.02	-0.01	0.01	0.02	-0.02	0.04

Source: Compiled and calculated from the data published in CMIE and moneycntrl.com

It is exhibited in the table 4 that the Return on Investment Ratio of selected Steel Companies in India from 2006-2007 to 2015 -2016. The average of Return on Investment Ratio of Steel companies shows a fluctuating trend during the study period.

It indicates that the overall efficiency of an enterprise. JSW Steel Limited has the highest average of 25.13 percent, followed by the Star ferro steel Limited which has the average of 22.52 percent. The Mukand steel Limited has the lowest level of the average of 7.66 percent.

The Jindal Saw Limited has the highest standard deviation of 18.61 percent, followed by VISA Steel Ltd which has the standard deviation is 17.80 percent. Ashirwad Steels Limited has lowest standard deviation of 2.20 percent.

Steel authority of India Limited has the highest co-efficient of variation of 120.68 percent, followed by the Bhushan Steel Limited of 101.67 percent. Ashirwad Steel Limited has the lowest co-efficient of variation of 22.07 percent.

JSW Steel Limited and Jindal Saw Steel Limited has the highest Compound Annual Growth Rate of 0.08 percent, followed by VISA Steel Limited of 0.07 percent. Usha Martin Limited has the negative Compound Annual Growth Rate of -0.05 percent.

Earnings Per Share

Table 5 Summaries Statistics of Earnings per Share ratio of the select Steel Companies in India during the period from 2006-2007 to 2015-2016

(In Percentage)

Year	Tata Steel	JSW Steel	Sail	Star Ferro	VISA Steel	Bhushan	Jindal Saw	Ferro Alloys	Usha Martin	Welspun steel	Mukand	APL Apollo	Jindal Steel	Ashirwad Steel	Bajaj Steel
2006-2007	72.74	70.09	15.02	18.20	9.13	73.76	21.33	10.62	21.20	14.60	12.76	4.48	22.30	2.10	27.10
2007-2008	63.85	90.84	18.25	17.55	7.87	99.77	34.85	10.86	15.79	10.19	8.12	21.10	20.34	8.35	21.58
2008-2009	69.70	72.96	14.95	13.26	13.92	99.20	169.39	12.66	15.86	19.77	-12.62	14.27	19.35	9.65	31.24
2009-2010	56.37	106.59	16.35	15.24	-6.07	99.09	64.17	11.54	13.03	12.52	8.48	.03	15.89	11.74	68.70
2010-2011	71.58	88.87	11.87	14.68	14.31	47.16	26.07	10.76	13.27	26.44	16.38	8.49	22.09	7.64	46.56
2011-2012	73.52	73.19	12.24	12.25	12.36	54.75	23.08	9.45	12.01	23.54	5.34	7.95	19.67	6.39	37.16
2012-2013	76.11	70.68	10.85	13.24	11.45	62.65	21.49	10.21	11.79	21.29	4.77	8.67	18.49	5.49	32.19
2013-2014	88.73	67.75	9.76	11.86	10.71	69.48	29.65	8.46	10.34	23.17	15.01	7.13	17.25	3.27	31.74
2014-2015	82.17	71.34	11.78	19.01	13.24	65.34	21.75	7.53	19.74	21.44	4.89	5.46	18.69	2.14	32.47
2015-2016	86.19	72.69	13.59	17.02	10.84	68.31	19.49	8.91	19.21	17.54	13.98	3.21	15.41	3.67	29.19
Mean	64.10	54.20	13.47	15.23	9.78	63.85	43.13	10.10	15.22	18.05	4.71	8.08	18.95	6.24	32.99
SD	9.87	21.71	2.65	2.58	5.93	43.85	46.29	1.53	3.76	6.87	6.62	5.94	2.33	3.14	17.04
CV	13.32	29.25	19.70	16.96	60.65	52.23	107.34	15.14	24.71	38.08	14.59	73.53	12.38	50.24	51.66
CAGR	0.02	0.01	-0.01	-0.01	-0.02	0.01	-0.01	-0.02	-0.01	0.02	0.01	-0.03	-0.02	-0.03	0.01

Source: Compiled and calculated from the data published in CMIE and moneycontrol.com

Table 5 reveals that the Earnings per share ratio of selected Steel Companies in India from 2006-2007 to 2015-2016. The average of Earnings per share ratio of steel companies shows a fluctuating trend during the study period. This fluctuation indicates whether or not be earnings power of the company has decreased. Bhushan Steel Limited has the highest average of 63.85 percent, followed by the JSW Steel Limited which has the average of 54.20 percent. This has been due to the more profit available per equity share. Mukand steel has the lowest average earning per share ratio of 4.71 percent

Jindal Saw limited has the highest standard deviation of 46.29 percent, followed by the Bhushan Steel limited which has the standard deviation of 3.85 percent. Jindal Steel Limited has the lowest standard deviation of 2.33 percent and it is found that it is stable in Earning per share ratio.

Jindal Steel Limited has the highest co-efficient of variation of 814.08 percent, followed by the Tata Steel Limited of 750.75 percent. Mukand Steel Limited has the lowest co-efficient of variation of 71.13 percent. It means high consistency of EPS ratio during the study period.

Tata steel limited and Welspun Steel Limited has the highest Compound annual growth rate of 0.02 percent, followed by the JSW Steel Limited, It is majority of the Steel Companies has

Compound annual growth rate of 0.1 percent. APL Apollo Steel Limited has negative Compound annual growth rate -0.03 percent.

Return on Capital Employed

Table 6 Summaries Statistics of return on capital employed ratio of the select steel companies in India during the period from 2006-2007 to 2015-2016

(In Percentage)

Year	Tata Steel	JSW Steel	Sail	Star Ferro	VISA Steel	Bhushan	Jindal Saw	Ferro Alloys	Usha Martin	Welspun steel	Mukand	APL Apollo	Jindal Steel	Ashirwad Steel	Bajaj Steel
2006-2007	4.64	5.12	1.86	3.21	2.10	3.54	4.12	7.56	3.29	2.14	7.61	9.71	3.29	2.17	4.84
2007-2008	5.69	3.52	4.12	2.28	5.22	1.86	3.36	5.84	5.12	1.86	12.21	10.84	4.14	1.16	5.69
2008-2009	8.73	4.27	3.27	2.06	4.31	3.51	5.61	6.39	8.16	1.52	11.04	12.16	3.69	3.28	3.99
2009-2010	12.96	3.98	5.44	-1.52	5.19	6.22	7.59	8.64	9.57	3.26	8.69	10.39	5.61	5.14	5.38
2010-2011	11.34	8.64	8.55	-2.89	12.74	5.19	8.37	6.81	7.63	3.78	5.39	13.75	8.38	3.19	8.39
2011-2012	14.77	13.22	1.91	-1.91	3.81	8.73	9.57	4.26	5.69	4.64	3.54	14.52	13.40	-6.32	16.50
2012-2013	12.80	12.59	6.67	-4.09	-2.97	6.95	7.61	13.96	8.02	6.18	2.74	14.51	9.57	2.72	10.89
2013-2014	13.37	12.96	4.60	16.88	0.32	4.29	6.74	17.47	8.21	4.84	6.19	12.57	7.51	1.26	18.95
2014-2015	9.25	12.72	5.43	11.62	-1.06	2.69	8.54	12.09	5.76	4.75	10.13	13.51	5.73	0.23	8.09
2015-2016	9.03	7.00	3.25	5.49	1.84	2.14	7.22	11.21	2.49	1.60	9.59	13.56	2.79	1.26	6.47
Mean	10.26	8.40	4.51	3.11	3.15	4.51	6.87	9.42	6.39	3.46	7.71	2.55	6.41	1.41	8.92
SD	3.37	4.13	2.10	6.70	4.32	2.24	1.97	4.15	2.31	1.63	3.19	1.73	3.34	3.06	5.09
CV	32.86	49.14	46.61	215.22	137.24	49.61	28.69	44.08	36.15	47.26	41.34	13.78	52.11	216.98	57.03
CAGR	0.07	0.03	0.06	0.06	-0.01	-0.05	0.06	0.04	-0.06	-0.03	0.02	0.03	-0.02	-0.05	0.03

Source: Compiled and calculated from the data published in CMIE and moneycontrol.com.

Table 6 reveals that the Return on Capital Employed of selected Steel Companies in India from 2006-2007 to 2015-2016. The average of Return on Capital Employed of steel companies shows a fluctuating trend during the study period. Tata Steel Limited has the highest average of 10.26 per cent; followed by the Bajaj Steel Limited which has the average of return on capital employed 8.92 percent. Ashirwad Steel Limited has the lowest average of return on capital employed 1.41 percent.

Star Ferro Steel Limited has the highest standard deviation of 6.70percent, followed by the Bajaj Steel Limited of 5.09 percent. Welspun Steel Limited has the lowest standard deviation of return on capital employed 1.63 percent.

Ashirwad Steel Limited has the highest co-efficient of variation 216.98 percent, followed by the Star Ferro Steel Limited of 215.22 percent. APL Apollo Steel Limited has the lowest co-efficient of variation of 13.78 percent. It is not consistent during the study period.

Tata Steel Limited has the highest Compound annual growth rate of 0.07 percent, followed by the SAIL, Star Ferro and Jindal Saw Limited which has the Compound annual growth rate of 0.06 percent, Usha martin ltd has the negative compound annual growth rate of -0.06 percent during the study period.

Panel Unit Root Test

H0: There is no panel unit root among the time series of Profitability ratios.

Table 7 Panel Unit Root Test of the Select Profitability Ratios of Select Steel Companies in India during the period from 2006-2007 to 2015-2016

Variable	Levin 't'				ADF				PP Fisher			
	Level		First difference		Level		First difference		Level		First difference	
	't' statistics	p value	't' statistic	p value	't' statistics	p value	't' statistic	p value	't' statistics	p value	't' statistic	p value
GP	-0.46684	0.3203	-6.45120	0.000	10.8652	0.8177	30.9042	0.0981	13.4831	0.6372	58.7033	0.0000
OP	-2.76446	0.0029	-2.36840	0.0089	22.8737	0.0624	44.8743	0.0122	29.7166	0.0083	103.070	0.0000
NP	-1.01445	0.1552	-	-	31.5741	0.2076	-	-	53.7180	0.0011	-	-
ROI	-2.62881	0.0043	-	-	28.1388	0.3517	-	-	48.0046	0.0054	-	-
EPS	-1.62997	0.0516	-9.6999	0.0000	12.1717	0.5925	59.2340	0.0002	17.1263	0.2495	145.668	0.0000
RCE	-3.13380	0.0009	-4.26536	0.0000	19.4091	0.2480	37.1671	0.0722	19.2227	0.2573	43.4528	0.0000

Source: Calculated by Eviews.

The table 7 shows the results of Panel Unit Root Test of Profitability ratios for the panel data of 15 Steel Companies. The presence of unit root is tested using Levin 't', ADF and PP Fisher. It is revealed from the table that the probability value of the time series of Profitability ratios is less than 0.05 for the majority of the test. Hence the null-hypothesis is rejected and it is concluded that the time series is stationary level. The results of panel unit root test confirm that the data series of gross profit, operating profit, net profit, return on investment, earnings per share and return on capital employed are integrated at the order zero is I(0).

Panel Co Integration Test

Analysis of Panel Co integration Test for the Profitability Ratios of Select Steel Companies in India during the period from 2006-2007 to 2015-2016

Table 8 Case -1 Individual intercept

	Statistic	Probability	Weighted Statistic	Probability
Panel v-Statistic	-2.794032	0.9974	-2.319767	0.9898
Panel rho-Statistic	0.339951	0.6331	1.353707	0.9121
Panel PP-Statistic	-6.559127	0.0000	-4.502251	0.0000
Panel ADF-Statistic	-0.329557	0.3709	0.288305	0.6134
Group rho-Statistic	2.515294	0.9941		
Group PP-Statistic	-5.593494	0.0000		
Group ADF-Statistic	1.968232	0.9755		

Table 9 Case - 2 Individual intercept and Individual trend

Statistic	Probability	Weighted Statistic	Probability
-4.479842	1.0000	-3.766399	0.9999
4.923501	1.0000	5.763342	1.0000
-6.689801	0.0000	-0.549758	0.2912
7.126663	1.0000		
-3.570831	0.0002		

Table 10 Case – 3 No intercept or trend

	Statistic	Probability	Weighted Statistic	Probability
Panel v-Statistic	-1.632735	0.9487	-1.811093	0.9649
Panel rho-Statistic	2.025563	0.9786	2.953007	0.9984
Panel PP-Statistic	-5.845957	0.0000	0.671558	0.7491
Panel ADF-Statistic	-4.446239	0.0000	0.522271	0.6993
Group rho-Statistic	4.670063	1.0000		
Group PP-Statistic	0.500243	0.6915		
Group ADF-Statistic	0.900939	0.8162		

Source: Compiled and Calculated by Eviews

The table 8 displays the results of 11 tests of panel co integration under the assumption of individual intercept. Based on the test result it is revealed that P value for majority of the test is more than 5% significant level. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted and it is concluded that there no long run relationship between the profitability ratios.

The panel co integration test under the assumption of Individual intercept and Individual trend is presented in table 9 it is inferred from the table that null hypothesis is accepted since Prob. Value is more than 0.05 for most of the result. It is concluded that there no co integration between the profitability ratios.

The table 10 reports panel co integration test under the assumption of No intercept or trend based on the test result it is revealed that P value for majority of the test is more than 5% significant level. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted and it is concluded that there no long run relationship between the profitability ratios.

Suggestion

- The Steel Company’s may concentrate on their cost of production, investment in fixed assets and their sales to improve their profitability.
- The Bhushan Steel Limited, Usha martin Limited and Ashirwad Steel Limited should try to increase the production so as to get economics of steel production. It will assist in raising the rate of return on capital employed.

Conclusion

India is the third-largest steel producer in the world, in 2016. The present study analyses the Productivity and Financial efficiency of the select Steel Companies in India from 2006-2007 to 2015-2016. The study found that even though the steel production has been increasing, the companies are not in a position to export more. It was also found that the financial position of the steel companies was not satisfactory. So the steel companies should design a balanced capital structure, use fixed assets efficiently, adopt credit policies, apply modern inventory and cash management systems and control operating costs to improve and maintain the financial performance in future.

References

- Ata Takeh & Jubiliy Navaprabha, “Capital Structure and Its Impact on Financial Performance of Indian Steel Industry”, *International Journal of Management (IJM)* ISSN 0976-6510, vol. 6, no. 6, 2015, pp. 29-38.
- Gurusamy, S & Asdha Krishnan, “Performance of the Companies Profitability”, *Gitam Journal of Management*, 2010.

Nishi Sharma, "Financial Analysis of Indian Automobile Industry", *IJRCM*, vol. 1, no. 9, 2011, pp. 112-116.

Thenmozhi, S & Tamilselvi, K, "Financial Health of Selected Iron and Steel Companies in India - Z Score Model", *International Journal in Management and Social Science (IJMSS)* ISSN: 2321-1784, vol. 03, no. 12.

Sudarsana Reddy, G, "The Financial Performance of Paper Industry in Andhra Pradesh", *Finance*, India, 2003.

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